

LINGUOCULTUROLOGY AS A NEW FIELD OF MODERN LINGUISTICS

Ismatova Nodirakhon Makhmudovna

A teacher of Kokand state pedagogical institute;

Ismatov Ravshan Murodullaevich

Abdumanonova Rayhon Avaz kizi

Students of Kokand state pedagogical institute; Chemistry department

Phone number: +998911523454

Email address: nodiraismatova1981@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10349592>

Abstract: In this article, the study of linguocultural science, which studies the closeness of language and culture, is researched as a separate direction of modern linguistics.

Key words: language, culture, anthropocentrism, linguoculturology, national language, language owners.

Linguistics is a comprehensive field of science that includes the study of cultural studies, ethnology, psychology and general linguistics. The traditional language, which is an object of study for linguistics, is described as a means of creating, developing and preserving culture in this field of science. The main focus of linguistic culture is aimed at classifying a particular world with the help of concepts that harmoniously form the linguistic landscape of the world. [1.32]

The main goal is to study such a phenomenon as "mental-linguistic complex", which implies a strict correlation between the structure of a language and the thinking of a language owner.

In the field of linguistic and cultural studies, which analyzes the relationship between language and culture, the level of expression of cultural views in language, the national-cultural, ancient and modern views of the peoples of the world, customs, traditions, and the characteristics of the expression of values in a certain national speech are analyzed. [2.12]

Another task of linguistics and cultural studies is the study of national and cultural means of language. In this case, we can see the expression of the character, appearance, behavior and speech of a person (representative of a nation) by poetic and prose texts, phraseology and metaphors, proverbs and proverbs as a linguistic and cultural phenomenon. They contain not only language markers, but also linguocultures.

The object of Linguistics is to study the interaction between the language that expresses information about the culture and the values and preferences associated with it, and the person who creates this culture using this language.

The object is studied at the intersection of several fundamental sciences, namely linguistics and cultural studies, ethnography and psycholinguistics.

In culture, having figurative, standard, pictorial-metaphorical meanings and summarizing the results of human consciousness, i.e. archetypal and prototypical myth, ritual, folklore and religious discourses, poetic and prose texts, phraseologisms and metaphors, signs and paremies Language units summarizing (proverbs and proverbs) are the subject of this subject.

Scholars interpret linguoculturalism in different ways. V.N. According to Telia, the object of linguo-cultural studies is not only cultural information within the nation, but also cultural information within the universal human sphere. For example, the cultural universals in the "Bible" and "Qur'an" corresponding to different peoples.

Lingvokulturology studies the relationship between language and culture, the expression and realization of ethnic mentality in language. The basis of linguistic culture is aimed at systematizing the specific features of the semantic signs of specific cultural concepts.

Y.M. Vereshagina and V.G. Kostomarov distinguishes between such types as linguo-national studies and linguo-cultural studies. According to them, linguistics studies the national realities specific to that language, which are reflected in one language. These are non-equivalent language units.

Language is closely related to culture. Language develops in culture and expresses it. Language preserves culture in its units and transmits it to generations. Linguistics is a science that emerged between linguistics and cultural studies and studies the reflection of the nation in language. Language collects and stores information of cultural significance. A. Abduazizov is a scientific researcher of e'itroficha, linvoculturology - language and culture, cross-cultural issues. This field studies not only culture, but through it various national traditions, religious phenomena, national concepts, means of conscious perception of the world through language. The language map of the world generally corresponds to their logical expression in the minds of people. A wider and deeper scientific study of this issue is related to linguocultural and linguocognitology.

Therefore, the goal of linguo-cultural studies is to preserve the culture manifested in its components of the language and to study the methods of its verbalization. The study of language through culture is becoming more and more important, therefore, at a time when a new field such as linguo-spiritual studies is emerging in modern linguistics and high results are expected, not to

study linguo-culturology, which has its own fundamental basis in linguistics for a long time, seems to be deviating from the development of science.

Lingvoculturology is a new trend of communicative linguistics today. Pragmatics is the study of the practical aspects of human action and thought. Furthermore, it is the study of the use of linguistic signs, words and sentences, in actual situations. Pragmatics outlines the study of meaning in the interactional context. It looks beyond the literal meaning of an utterance and considers how meaning is constructed as well as focusing on implied meanings. It considers language as an instrument of interaction, what people mean when they use language and how we communicate and understand each other.

Linguoculturological approach in teaching English focuses on the semantic concept. Through this angle the process of learning the English language implies not only traditional study of phonetics, grammar, and vocabulary but also the English language mastering through its national concepts. This enables the learners to acquire interrelated ethno cultural knowledge of language, culture and history, resulting in formation of linguo-cultural competence, which is a set of special skills necessary to use in practice.

In Dictionary of English Language and Culture it is defined as ability to do what is needed (2005). It means that a student should be able to develop an ability to recognize and connect a semantic content of a language symbol with associative motivation of choice of a word. In a number of works of Russian scientists the concept "competency" is defined as intellectual and personal ability of an individual to practical activities, and "competence" as content's component of the given ability in the form of knowledge, skills and aptitudes (Zimnyaya, 2003). In Zimnyaya's opinion competency always displays the actual competence (2003). Linguoculturology has to deal with lots of issues related to the language, such as the role of culture in formation of linguistic concepts, connection between the linguistic symbol and cultural sense of the word. It is essential to identify cultural semantics which can be obtained from the interaction of two different fields - language and culture. Language and culture interactions have a reciprocal relationship: language shapes cultural interactions and cultural interactions shape language.

It should be noted that the relationship of language to culture involves many difficult and contradictory problems. One problem may occur when cultural information of linguistic items mainly acquires some implication, which is hidden. A wellknown expression "French leave" means 'leave or absence without permission'. Originally it was used as a term describing a custom,

prevalent in France in the 18th century but regarded in England as impolite, of leaving a social function without saying farewell to one's host or hostess. It is now used of any unauthorized absence or departure, from one's place of work.

References:

1. Воробьев В.В. Лингвокультурология: (Теория и методы) – Москва, 1997. – С. 32.
2. Красных В.В. Этнопсихоллингвистика и лингвокультурология. Москва, 2002. – С. 12.
3. Popova, E. I. (2022). The Principle of Philology and Philological Analysis of the Word. International Journal of Social Science Research and Review, 5(8), 165-169.
4. Попова, Е. И. (2019). Семантическая обусловленность переносного употребления временных форм русского глагола. Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире, (2-3), 99-104.
5. Popova, E. I. (2023). FEATURES OF THE FUNCTIONAL CLASSIFICATION OF SENTENCES ACCORDING TO THE PURPOSE OF THE STATEMENT. Gospodarka i Innowacje., 35, 138-141.
6. Попова, Е. И. (2017). Информативные таблицы как средство формирования познавательной активности студентов. In Молодежь и наука: реальность и будущее (pp. 297-302).
7. CASES OF FIGURATIVE USE OF THE MODERN FORMS OF THE RUSSIAN VERB. (2023). Boletín De Literatura Oral , 10(1), 2552-2559. <http://www.boletindeliteraturaoral.com/index.php/bdlo/article/view/534>
8. Попова, Е. И. (2023). ПРИРОДА И ЭВОЛЮЦИЯ ОБСТАНОВОЧНОЙ РЕМАРКИ. Gospodarka i Innowacje., 41, 146-151.
9. Popova, E. I. (2023). TECHNIQUES OF SEMANTIZATION OF RUSSIAN VOCABULARY IN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE AUDIENCE. Open Access Repository, 4(03), 227-234.
10. Makhmudovna, I. N. (2022). TOPONYMS CONSTRUCTED BY COMPOUND NOUNS WITH THE COLOR COMPONENT. Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities, 2(1.6 Philological sciences).
11. Makhmudovna, I. N. (2022). Some Types of Toponyms. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION, 2(2), 478-480.
12. Makhmudovna, I. N. (2022). Generallegislation of toponymics and the concept of toponymy. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 12(5), 704-706.
13. Ismatova, N. M. (2022). TOPONYMS EXPRESSED IN ENGLISH WITH A COMPOUND NOUN WITH A COLOR COMPONENT. In Современные проблемы

филологии и методики преподавания языков: вопросы теории и практики (pp. 101-104).

14. Гончарова, Н. В. (2015). Использование приёма беседы при изучении рассказа В. Распутина " Уроки французского" в студенческой аудитории. In Молодежь и наука: реальность и будущее (pp. 385-387).

15. Vasilievna, G. N. THE THEME OF LONELINESS IN THE STORIES OF L. PETRUSHEVSKAYA.

